

**THE CONCEPTUAL STUDY OF URDHWAGA AMLAPITTA AND ITS HETU
(ETIOLOGICAL FACTOR) ACCORDING TO AYURVEDA AND MODERN SCIENCE****Prerna P. Raut*¹, Madhavi R. Khuje², Jaii Kini³**¹Asst. Professor and PhD Scholar, Rognidana, RRK Ayurved College Murtijapur.²Asso. Professor, Vilasrao Deshmukh Ayurved College, Mauda, Nagpur.³Proff. and HOD Rognidan YMT Ayurved College, Kharghar, Navi Mumbai.***Corresponding Author: Prerna P. Raut**

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ABSTRACT

Improper lifestyle and irregular diet and sleep schedule have made people prone to various diseases like hyperacidity. In Ayurveda Hyperacidity can be correlated with *Amlapitta* specially *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* symptomatically. Acharya *Kashyapa* have clearly indicated that the *Grahani Dosha* and *Amapitta* occur in the person who could not check timings and temptation of diet and sleep after taking meal in day time. Acharya *Charaka* has clearly indicated that the *Grahani Dosha* and *Amapitta* occur in the person who could not check timings and temptation of diet. In this article, we are reviewing the causative factor of *Amlapitta* given my Our Acharya in Various *Samhitas* like *Kashyapa* and *Madhavnidana*. Also We are studying modern Etiological factor responsible for Hyperacidity. The *Aharaj* and *Viharaj Hetu* given my *Samhita* are important to study as this disease got worsened if not followed proper *Pathya*.

KEYWORDS: *Urdhwaga Amlapitta, Grahani Dosha, Aharaj Hetu, Viharaj Hetu, Pathya.***INTRODUCTION**

Now-a-days modernization, entire civilization changed all the means of our lifestyle patterns. In metropolitan cities like Mumbai, Chennai, etc. specially night workers have improper lifestyle and irregular diet and sleep schedule have made people prone to various diseases like hyperacidity. According to population based studies 16.2% of urban Indian population have Hyperacidity. Hyperacidity is one of such conditions which aggravate due to unhealthy lifestyle and dietary habit. The term Hyperacidity in particular refers to a condition in which stomach contains an excessive amount of Hydrochloric Acid. It could be described as a disorder of the modern and urban cities where the lifestyle habits of people are quit irregular and unhealthy. Hyperacidity leads to many diseases such as gastric ulcers, peptic ulcer in advance condition. The long continued existence of hyper acidic fluid in stomach is to induce severe Gastritis accompanied by numerous erosion of mucus membrane.

In Ayurveda, Hyperacidity can be correlated with *Amlapitta* specially *Urdhwaga Amlapitta* symptomatically; as *Adhoga Amlapitta* is rarely found. In *Brihatrayi*, *Amlapitta* is not mentioned as a separate disease entity but there are several references in *Charaka Samhita* regarding *Amlapitta* while Acharya *Kashyapa* and *Madhava* have described this disease as separate entity with detailed description. Acharya *Kashyapa* have clearly indicated that the *Grahani Dosha* and *Amapitta* occur in the person who could not check timings and temptation of diet and sleep after taking meal in day time. Acharya *Charaka* has clearly indicated that the *Grahani Dosha* and *Amapitta* occur in the person who could not check timings and temptation of diet. *Ajirna* after encountering the specific *Doshas* and affinity with specific site may cause various diseases. *Annavisha* i.e. Aama produced due to *Ajirna* when with *Pittadi Doshas* and lodges in Aamashaya then it produces *Amlapittadi Vyadhi*. Acharya *Charaka* have clearly indicated that the *Grahani Dosha* and *Amapitta* occur in the person who could not check timings and temptation of diet and sleep

after taking meal in day time. Acharya Kashyapa has mentioned that after intake of etiological factors, Agni is vitiated which leads to *Amotpatti* and vitiation of *Pitta Dosh*. This further results into fermentation. As a result, *Shukratwa* gets established in the *Aamashaya*, due to which even *Supachya Ahara* if taken, it will get fermented producing the *vyadhi Amlapitta*.

In this article, we are reviewing the causative factor of *Amlapitta* given by our Acharya in various *Samhitas* like *Kashyapa* and *Madhavidana*. Also we are studying modern etiological factor responsible for hyperacidity. The *Aharaj* and *Viharaj Hetu* given by *Samhita* are important to study as this disease got worsened if not followed proper *Pathya*.

REVIEW OF AMLAPITTA

Amlapitta is composed of two words.

Amla + Pitta = Amlapitta.

The term *Amla* refers to a particular type of taste equated with the sour taste which causes excessive salivary secretion. *Pitta* is a chemical substance which is mainly responsible for the maintenance of the process of digestion, transformation and transmutation. On combining both these words the term *Amlapitta* implies to a disease or condition in which the.

wa Definition : *Amlapitta* comprises two terms viz. 'Amla' and 'Pitta'.

NIDANAPANCHAKA OF AMLAPITTA

List of *Hetus* of *Amlapitta* is compiled by Acharya and many recent scholars. Acharya Kashyapa has described both endogenous and exogenous types of causative factors. Though Acharya Charaka had not given directly *Hetus* responsible for *Amlapitta*; but by applying *Tarka*, *Hetus* can be listed from various places in *Charaka*

Samhita e.g. *Grahani Chikitsa Adhyaya* (Cha.Chi.15 /43).

NIDANA

Hetu Cha. Chai. 15, Ka. Khi. 16, Ma. Ni. 51

In *Kashyapa Samhita* and *Madhava Nidana*, *Aaharaja Hetus* are described in details. *Aaharaja Hetus* can be again subdivided into two subgroups. viz.

- Nidanas* related to *Aahara Vidhi Vidhana*
- Nidanas* related to *Aahara Dravyas*

i. *Nidanas* related to *Aahara Vidhi Vidhana*

- Adhyashana* (Overeating)
- Ajirnahana* (Food intake without digestion of previous food)
- Akale Bhojana* - It is one of the part of *Vishamashana*. (Eating at improper timings)
- Aame Aame cha puranat* (Successive intake without digestion of previous food)
- Atyushna Aahara* (Excessively hot)
- Atisnigdha Aahara* (Excessively Unctuous)
- Ati Gorasa Sevana* (Excessive intake Milk and its derivatives)
- Atiruksha Aahara* (Excessively dry food)
- Atidrava Aahara* (Excessively liquid diet)
- Ati Antarodakapana* (Intake of excessive water during meal)
- Kale Anashanat* - It is one of the part of *Vishamashana*. (Not eating at proper time)
- Ati Guru Aahara* (Excessively heavy diet)
- Vishamashana* (Eating untimely or in excess or less quantity)
- Viruddha Aahara* (Food having antagonistic potencies)

Table no. 1: Showing *Aharaj hetu* of *Amlapitta*.

Sr	<i>Nidanas</i>	K.S	M.N	B.P	Y.R	S.N	REF
1	<i>Kulatthasevana</i>	+					<i>k.s khil16-3-6</i>
2	<i>Pulakasevana</i>	+					
3	<i>Guru ahara sevana</i>	+					
4	<i>Abhishyandi ahara</i>	+					
5	<i>Ati snigdha ahara</i>	+					
6	<i>Ati ruksha ahara</i>	+					
7	<i>Pishtanna sevana</i>	+					
8	<i>Apakva anna sevana</i>	+					
9	<i>Phanita sevana</i>	+					
10	<i>Ikshuvikara sevana</i>	+					
11	<i>Paryushita anna sevana</i>	+					
12	<i>Bhurjitadhanya sevana</i>	+					
13	<i>Ati ushnanna sevana</i>	+					
14	<i>Adhyashana</i>	+					
15	<i>Atidrava</i>	+					
16	<i>Ajirnebhajana</i>	+					
17	<i>Madhyasavana</i>	+					
18	<i>Go rasavarga sevana</i>	+					
19	<i>Annahinamadhya sevana</i>	+					
20	<i>Antrodakapana</i>	+					

21	Akalebhojanam	+				+	s.namlapiita adhikar373-378
22	Akaleanashana	+				+	
23	Vishamashana	+				+	
24	Vidahianna sevana		+	+	+		Ma.ni 15/1 b.p 10/1
25	Vidahipana sevana		+	+	+		y.ramlapiitaadhikaruutara237
26	Dushtanna sevan		+	+	+		
27	Viruddhashana		+	+	+	+	
28	Atiamla sevana		+	+	+	+	
29	Kaphaprapakopianna sevana		+	+	+	+	
30	Vidagdhaahara sevana			+	+		
31	Pitta prakoaana sevana			+	+		
32	Ati tikshana sevan						
33	Katuannapana sevana	+					
34	Vega vidharan	+					
35	Bhukte diwa swapna	+					
36	Bhuktaatyashana	+					
37	Bhuktaavagahan	+					

Table No. 2: Etiological factor according to modern science.

Sr no	Dietary factor
1.	Fast eating
2.	Eating junk food
3.	Eating while watching tv or mobile
4.	Eating with tea or coffee
5.	Overeating
6.	Stressful eating
7.	Late night eating

VIHARAJA HETUS

1. Atisnana (Excessively taking bath)
2. Avagahana (Excess of swimming)
3. Bhuktwa Bhukta Diwaswapa (Sleeping in day time after meal)
4. Vegavidharana (Not attending natural urges)
5. Shayya Prajagaraihi (Not sleeping at proper time and for adequate hours)

Etiological factor according to modern science

1. Alcohol consumption
2. Smoking
3. Obesity
4. NSAIDS
5. Lying down within 3 hours after eating
6. Working in seating position for long time.
7. Night shift duties.
8. Lack of physical activity.

BHEDA (classification)

Table No. 4: Showing bheda of Amlapitta.

According to Archarya Kashyapa	According to Archarya Madhava
VatikaAmlapitta	SanilaAmlapitta
PaittikaAmlapitta	SanilaKaphaAmlapitta
SlesmikaAmlapitta	SakaphaAmlapitta
	SlesmapittaAmlapitta
	According to Gati-
	1 Udravagata Amlapitta
	2 Adhogata Amlapitta

PURVARUPA

In Ayurvedic classics, no specific purvarupas of Amlapitta are mentioned. But by applying Tarka and practical experiences; some important inferences can be drawn. Agnimandya, Ajirna are the successive stages of Amlapitta.

RUPA OF AMLAPITTA

Sr	Rupa	K.S	M.N	B.P	Y.R	S.N
1	Avipaka		+	+	+	
2	Klama		+	+	+	+
3	Utklesha		+	+	+	
4	Tiktodgara		+	+	+	
5	Amlodgara		+	+	+	+
6	Gaurava		+	+	+	
7	HridDaha	+	+	+	+	+
8	KanthaDaha	+	+	+	+	+
9	Aruchi		+	+	+	
10	Vidbheda	+				
11	Gurukosthata	+				
12	Amlakosthata	+				
13	Shiroruja	+				+
14	Hridshoola	+				
15	Adhmana	+				
16	Angasada	+				
17	Roma harsha	+				
18	Antrakujana	+				
19	Urovidaha	+				
20	Tiktasyata					+

Samprapti presentation based on Kriyakala**UPASHAYA – ANUPASHAYA**

The factors which relieve the signs and symptoms of a disease are called as *Upashaya*, while the factors which increase the signs and symptoms of a disease are called as *Anupashaya*.

Only Acharya *Kashyapa* has explained the *Upashaya* and *Anupashaya* of *Amlapitta*.

These are according to types of *Amlapitta* as follows:

Vataja Amlapitta : *Snigdha Upashaya*
Pittaja Amlapitta : *Swadu and Shita Upashaya*
Kaphaja Amlapitta : *Ruksha and Ushna Upashaya*

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Amlapitta is a dominant disease in the present scenario of unhealthy food habits and regimens. The *Brahtrayi Granthas* has a scattered references about the *Amlapitta*. Acharya *Madavakara* has divided *Amlapitta* into *Urdwva* and *Adhwa* on the basis of *Doshagati* and *Madavanidana* is a compilation of all *Samhitas* about *hetu* and *Samprapti* of *Amlapitta*. but *Kashya Samhita* and *Madhava Nidan* gave detail description of the disease and its all causative factors in detail. It includes *Ahar Vidhi* related, *Ahar janya* and *Vihar janya Hetu*. Acharya *Kashyap* also main that *Amlapitta* ia more prominent in *Anoopa Desha* so, advice for change of place in *Amlapitta* treatment also considered where the Acharya says to change the habitat where all the above treatment modality fails. Acharya says *Amlapitta* is more common in marshy land so one should be away from the *Desha* which is more prone for it.

The etiological factor plays important role in Diagnosis as well as treatment of *Amlapitta*. Detail study of *Hetu* given in *Samhita* can be co relate with todays etiological factor. we observe close resemblance with current lifestyle and food habits which cause *Amlapitta*. Stress is important cause of *Amlapitta* we observe today which has mentioned in *Samhitas*.

*Pathya**Apathya* is key for preventing the disease. In *Amlapitta*, *Pathya* *Apatya* plays very crucial role, as we gave treatment but if patient countinue consuming its trigger factor, treatment is likely to fail or does not respond on treatment.

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